

Response to “Mirror of the Unknown”

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This is a comment in response to “Mirror of the unknown: should research on mirror-image molecular biology be stopped?” (see [Nature 645, 588–591; 2025](#)) by Ting Zhu (Westlake University, Hangzhou, China)

We thank Prof. Zhu for advancing the conversation on mirror life. We agree that mirror biomolecules offer potential benefits and that mirror bacteria could pose immunological and ecological risks, a conclusion that other scientists have endorsed.¹ We strongly agree that mirror life should not be created without clear evidence of safety.

Prof. Zhu correctly notes that glycans “exhibit less uniform chirality than do proteins, DNA and RNA.” Because both enantiomers are found in the glycocalyx in nature, the glycans on the surface of mirror bacteria may provoke some immune response. Other immune mechanisms that might maintain efficacy against mirror bacteria include some antimicrobial peptides, parts of the complement system, and possibly certain non-canonical T cells.

Nevertheless, many other immune mechanisms, including most pattern recognition receptors, antigen presentation, T cell activation, antibody production, parts of the complement system, and phagocytosis, are expected to fail at least partially. Deficiencies in even a single immune pathway frequently prove fatal.² The immune system would therefore likely offer inadequate protection against mirror bacteria infection.

Prof. Zhu thoughtfully discusses the need for checkpoints on the road to mirror life. Once a technology exists, the knowledge to replicate it becomes widely accessible and governance becomes difficult.³ This suggests we must consider a critical question: which technological precursors must we choose not to build because doing so means we can no longer reliably prevent the creation of mirror life? Global discussion about where to establish boundaries while protecting beneficial research must continue with broad participation.

References

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3. Evans, J. H., Callender, C., Devaraj, N. K., Isaacs, F. J., & Kaebnick, G. E. (2025). Building Decision Points Into Research’s Slipperiest Slopes. *Issues in Science and Technology*, 41(4), 78-82. <https://issues.org/mirror-life-slippery-slope-decision-points/>